

complexes. Thus the Cu^{II} complexes have most probably distorted octahedral structure.

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Synthesis and Characterisation of Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Copper(II) and Zinc(II) Complexes with Tridentate Schiff Base Vanillideneanthranilic Acid

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CCOORDINATION ability of different Schiff bases derived from anthranilic acid and their analytical applications have been studied extensively¹⁻⁵. However, Schiff bases derived from vanillin and

amino acids have not been fully investigated. In continuation of our earlier work^{6,7} on vanillideneanthranilic acid complexes of transition metal ions, we report here the results of magnetic and infrared spectroscopic investigations of some new Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} metal complexes of the above ligand.

Experimental

The ligand vanillideneanthranilic acid (C₁₅H₁₃NO₄; hereafter H₃L) was prepared⁸ by condensing an ethanolic solution of vanillin (1.52 g, 0.01 mol) and anthranilic acid (1.36 g, 0.01 mol), m.p. 174° (Found: C, 66.42; H, 4.80; N, 5.08. C₁₅H₁₃NO₄ calcd. for: C, 66.40; H, 4.83; N, 5.17%).

All metal chlorides used were of A.R. grade.

Isolation of metal chelates: Metal chloride (0.01 mol) and the ligand (0.01 mol) in methanol (20 ml) were refluxed together on a water-bath for 2 h. Metal chelates which separated on cooling were filtered, washed with methanol and finally dried in vacuum. The results of analytical data⁹ are recorded in Table 1.

Physical measurements: The molar conductance of the complexes were measured in nitrobenzene and/or methanol. The magnetic susceptibility measurements were made on a Gouy balance at room temperature using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as calibrant. Molecular weights were determined by a Gallenkamp semimicro ebulliometer using dioxan as the solvent. The ir spectra of the ligand and the complexes in nujol were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 257 spectrophotometer and Fourier far-ir spectra were recorded in a Polytec FIR 30 spectrometer. Thermograms were taken using a Stanton TR-1 recording thermobalance.

Results and Discussion

Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} form 1:1 complexes with vanillideneanthranilic acid. Elemental analysis data of these complexes are given in Table 1. All the complexes are stable against light and atmosphere. The complexes exhibit molar conductance in the range 0.01–7.3 Ω⁻¹ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and are non-electrolytes. The magnetic moments of the com-

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND THERMAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Colour	Mol. wt Found/ (Calcd.)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		ΛM Ω ⁻¹ cm ²	μ _{eff} B.M.	% Loss Found/ (Calcd.)	Decomp. Temp. (peak) K
			Metal	N				
[CoL(H ₂ O)] ₂	Pale pink	546.5 (696.4)	16.16 (16.88)	4.05 (4.04)	7.31	4.73	80 (76.85)	643
[NiL(H ₂ O)] ₂	Pale green	589.4 (694.7)	17.00 (16.98)	4.03 (4.05)	7.31	3.88	80 (78.40)	673
[CuL(H ₂ O)] ₂	Green	555.8 (705.6)	18.00 (18.12)	3.70 (3.99)	0.01	1.84	74 (77.92)	543
[ZnL(H ₂ O)] ₂	Silvery white	560.5 (709.2)	18.97 (18.54)	4.02 (3.97)	1.45	Dis	78 (76.91)	623

* LH₃ = C₁₅H₁₃NO₄.

plexes calculated from the corrected magnetic susceptibilities determined at room temperature are given in Table 1. The small variation can be accounted for by assuming dimeric or chain polymeric structures in the solid state⁹. Molecular weight determinations in dioxan support dimeric structure.

The ir spectrum of the ligand has a band of medium intensity at $\sim 1690\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a strong band at 1620 cm^{-1} . The first band can be assigned to the asymmetric carbonyl stretch of the COOH group and is totally absent in the spectra of the complexes. This is replaced by a very strong band at 1600 cm^{-1} which is due to the coordinated carboxylate ion. Unfortunately, this then obscures the C=N band that is located at 1620 cm^{-1} in the free ligand. There is, however, no sign of a shoulder on the 1600 cm^{-1} band, and it can be assumed that because of coordination, the C=N stretch has been displaced to lower wavenumbers and is obscured by the more intense carboxylate band.

In the complexes, the presence of coordinated water is confirmed by the observation of a double hump around 3300 cm^{-1} due to ν_{OH} . The coordinated nature of the water molecule is further confirmed by the appearance of a rocking mode of medium intensity at 860 cm^{-1} . The strong band found around 1280 cm^{-1} in the ligand is assigned to phenolic C—O stretching vibration¹⁰. The shift towards higher frequency side indicates bonding of the phenolate oxygen. In the present complexes the asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of the carboxyl group occur at $1590\text{--}1600$ and $1440\text{--}1445\text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively, with a difference $\Delta\nu_{\text{COO}}$ of $145\text{--}160\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Monodentate carboxylate group has a difference of $150\text{--}160\text{ cm}^{-1}$, but a bidentate or bridging carboxylate has a much closer difference ($< 120\text{ cm}^{-1}$)^{11,12}. Monodentate carboxylate groups are, therefore, indicated in the above chelates. The medium and somewhat broad intense band found in the region $460\text{--}480\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ vibration. Medium intensity bands appearing at $350\text{--}370\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for these metal complexes are tentatively assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ vibration^{13,15}.

The observed mass loss agreed fairly well with the value calculated from pyrolytic experiments. In the present complexes, it was observed that the decomposition started only after 250° . So the water present was the coordinated water¹⁶. The initial decomposition temperature was frequently used to define the relative thermal stability of the metal complexes¹⁶. On the basis of the experimental findings, the relative thermal stability¹⁷ for the vanillideneanthranilic acid metal complexes can be given as $\text{Co}^{\text{II}} \approx \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} > \text{Zn}^{\text{II}} > \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$.

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Complexes of Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Palladium(II), Zinc(II), Cadmium(II), Mercury(II) and Lead(II) with Glutathione

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RECENTLY, considerable interest has been shown in the binding of metal ions with amino acids and peptides as models for their interaction with proteins. Interaction of Zn^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Mn^{II} , Hg^{II} , Ag^{I} and Pd^{II} with glutathione (a tripeptide) was studied in solution by potentiometrically, spectrophotometrically and polarographically by various workers¹⁻⁹. These works prompted us to prepare Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Pb^{II} , Hg^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes with glutathione. The complexes were characterised by chemical analyses, magnetic moment data,